

IMIA WG Language and Meaning in Biomedicine Report for the Year July 2016 – June 2017

Website of the WG:

<http://imia-medinfo.org/wp/language-and-meaning-in-biomedicine/>

LinkedIn of the WG:

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3680642>

Chair (2015-2018)

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Vice-Chair (2012 – 2017)

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Vice-Chair (2015 – 2017)

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1. Background – Brief description of the WG mission, vision, and objective

IMIA's WG Language and Meaning in Biomedicine (formerly known as the Medical Concept Representation Working Group up to 2014) is an international forum for state-of-the-art dialogue and collaboration on semantics in healthcare and biomedical research, encompassing language, biomedical terminologies and ontologies. Since its formation, the working group was charged with: (1) Reviewing health data terminology and classification needs for the world community; (2) Evaluating information processing technology in meeting these defined needs; and (3) Recommending methods for future terminology systems.

1. Achievement - Events and projects conducted and publications completed

Successful submission for Medinfo 2017: Workshop “Unstructured Clinical Data Reuse for Precision Medicine: Current Status and Future Progress”

1. Participation - Engagement and participation in IMIA and health informatics events and activities

Presentation at Nursing Informatics 2016: Fernandez-Luque L, Vilmarlund V, Borycki E, Schulz S, Kuziemycki C, Marschollek M, Kulikowski CA. Social Media as Catalyzer for Connected Health: Hype or Hope? Perspectives from IMIA Working Groups. Stud Health Technol Inform. 2016;225:602-4.

1. **Outreach** - Recruitment and engagement of new members and target communities, publicity and representation at major events and/or on social media

The LinkedIn group has over 100 members. In this group the WG leadership aims to publish regular updates on relevant events.

1. **Collaboration** - Working with other IMIA WG/SIGs or external organizations or institutions

The WG participated in the preparation of a manuscript which is submitted as white paper for JAMIA, in collaboration with the JAMIA KR+S WG